

METHODS OF DEVELOPING SCIENTIFIC WORLD VIEW IN STUDENTS THROUGH FINE ART LESSONS

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INTRODUCTION. Fine arts, readers, creative activity, aesthetic feeling and intellectual development in ensuring an important role plays. Fine art classes, only artistic skills is not, but scientific outlook and also in the formation serve will. This article describes the fine arts through educational scientific outlook of development of the methods discussed will be.

MAIN PART. Scientific outlook and fine san'at. Scientific outlook and fine art and between relationship, education, and creative activities have an important role to have. Scientific outlook, human nature, society, and self-realize the attitude determines. Fine art while, artistic creativity and aesthetic sense of the emotions of the expression of a tool as, scientific knowledge and the formation of help will. This article describes the scientific outlook and fine arts of mutual communication and development the role discussed will be.

Scientific outlook concept. Scientific outlook — this man, nature, society, and self-consciousness of the connection. Her scientific knowledge, logic thinking and research methods of their into gets. Scientific outlook of development — that of education, the main targets of one. His main elements:
Research: the universe of the study, the experiment is out go and facts based on evidence production.

Logic thinking: manttiqiy and analysis with thinking, problems solving to ability.
Organization: knowledge extending continuing and them to society applied make.

Fine arts, artistic creation of forms, one is, the visual image, the colors, are kompozitsiya and form using feel-emotions, ideas, and the concept it represents. His main elements:

Color: aesthetic impact of the formation, emotional reactions address wake.

Composition: elements of mutual communication, visual order established was.

Check: fine arts expressed the ideas, characters and understand.

Fine arts, readers aesthetic of thought development with together, the scientific outlook to the formation also help you will. Her through, students:

Art definition, the kompozitsiya and colors learn. Artistic creation, man's beauty-enhancing mean, it feel to , and aesthetic experience that ensures.

Creative thinking and the development of. Fine arts, creative thinking in the development of an important role to have. Creative in the process, children with different ideas, the concept and the image will create, that while their intellectual abilities increases.

The universe understand and imagine to the ability of the expansion. Fine arts, students among communication encourages. A group activity, art projects and exhibitions through, students own thoughts and feeling-feelings of others with they will share.

Fine art lessons in scientific outlook of development of methods of

Research conduct. Fine arts course in research methods in the application, readers are real phenomena of study, experiment out to go to and the results of analyze to motivate. These methods are:

Readers that aspiring increases.

Them independent thinking stimulates.

Competitions. Fine art on competitions, readers creative abilities to increase help will. They have their own artistic developments of the public to demonstrate to you the opportunity to have will. This:

Scientific outlook of development, the service will.

Their effectiveness and evaluate the opportunity to gives.

The project works. Students creative projects implementation to increase, of them the scientific research of abilities to increase help will. Project work during, the students have little knowledge, abilities , and creative is a show they can.

CONCLUSION. Scientific outlook and fine art between communication, education in the process the important elements is one of the.fine art classes, educational scientific outlook in the development of an effective tool as serve will. Research methods, interactive methods, multimedia, a tools and creative projects, readers thinking, creativity to the survey take to go to the abilities you will develop. These techniques effective implementation to, readers, aesthetic, rational and creative development to ensure help will. Fine art, obviously, education is in the process of vital and creative approach require will. Fine arts education in the effective use, children of scientific outlook of development and their creative abilities to increase help will.

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